

The Essence And Main Functions Of Media Text

Mashkhura Makhamadjonova
Teacher of CAMU International Medical University

Abstract: *In this article, the concepts of media, media text, media stereotypes, media competence and media literacy, their scientific and analytical aspects, opinions on the research of these concepts are analyzed. Also, important signs of media text, their tasks and levels were studied and analyzed.*

Keywords — text, media text, context, literacy, mass communication, media, mass, integrative.

INTRODUCTION.

In today's fast-paced modern world, technologies are developing, and the speed of information dissemination is accelerating in the era of advanced news.

There are different opinions on the concept of media literacy, according to the American International Encyclopedia of Society, "Media is the ability of a person to be active and educated while feeling the reality of the whole world, to be able to understand, create, analyze and evaluate media texts, it means to be able to think critically, to be able to understand the socio-cultural and political content of modern media".

The term "media text", which appeared in English-language scientific literature in the 90s of the 20th century, quickly spread both in international academic circles and in national mass media. The main categories of media text are medianess (embodiment of the text using one or another media, determination by the format and technical capabilities of the channel), mass (both in the field of production and consumption of media products), integrative or multi-coded text (unification of various semiotic codes integration into a communicative whole), meaning-content, compositional structure and openness of the text at a certain level.

Media texts representing the concept of media and related phenomena are becoming more and more active. Media text is the result of media reality, and it is information in various forms of media, i.e. articles in newspapers and magazines, theses, shows and programs broadcast on television, clips, films, movies, videos on the Internet, gifs, animations, and all types of messengers. is the information conveyed through pictorial and graphic signs. Today, media text refers to the concrete result of media production, a media product, which consists of information and is a message presented in any type and genre of media (newspaper article, TV show, video clip, advertising message, film, etc.) to a mass audience. will be directed.

The main tasks of the media text are to prepare the growing young generation for life in modern information conditions, to perceive various information, to teach a person to understand it, to be aware of its consequences, the impact on the future English language teacher and his psyche. learning consists in mastering communication methods based on non-verbal forms of communication using technical means.

Analysis of different approaches to determining the essence and goals of the media text allows to distinguish the main elements of its content:

- to develop critical thinking of future English language teachers
- acquisition of media analysis and interpretation skills;
- determining methods of working with mass media;
- purposeful use of resources (media texts).

Researchers emphasize the interdisciplinary nature of media text, because "it is closely related not only to pedagogy and artistic education, but also to such fields of humanities as art studies (including film criticism, literary studies, theater criticism), cultural studies, and history. (in particular, history of world art culture and art), psychology (psychology of art, artistic perception, creativity) and others not only meet the needs of modern pedagogy in personal development, but also expand its scope. First of all, this is clearly visible in the methods and forms of training with future English language teachers. The analysis of media stereotypes by A.V. Federova defines the importance of determining and analyzing the plot, events, ideas, stereotypes of the media texts. A media stereotype reflects the attitude established in society towards one or another object. "Media stereotypes mean schematic, environment-adapted, habitual, fixed ideas about people, ideas, events, social phenomena, genres that have priority in media texts intended for mass audiences."

The analysis of media stereotypes relies on "media agency" ("source of information"), "media text category", "media text language", "media technology", "media category", "media audience" and other such key concepts of media education. .

Media agency (producers of media text, source of media information, media industry) — organizations, group of individuals (authors, producers, managers, etc.), usually includes a set of media texts and technical means that are created and distributed for mass audiences.

Media category — various types (press, television, cinematography, etc.), forms and genres, media texts.

The audience of media education (addressees) is a group of people for whom the media text is intended (students, teachers, media workers - media libraries, educational television stations).

Media technology — 1) equipment, instruments and materials necessary for creating media texts; 2) methods of creating media texts.

Media language is a set of expressive methods and tools used to create a specific media text. Media can "communicate" with the student, the user, in an artistic or audiovisual language. Collective methods and tools are used to create concrete media texts. For example, film and television using visual and sound media use audiovisual language, press language is combined with verbal (printed text) and pictorial (illustrations, photographs) images.

Media re-presentation is the expression process of human life society (people, events, ideas) in the media text.

I.A. Jurin, D.V. Zalagaev, B.A. Iskakov, O.P. Kutkina, N.A. Legotina, T.I. Myasnikova, A.V. Fedorov, I.M. Khijnnyak and others managed to create pedagogical models deemed necessary for multifaceted and timely effective pedagogical activity. those who A. V. Fedorov in his views on the development of media competence in future English language teachers separately points out "content and target, diagnostic and result components". It includes "a block of theoretical and historical preparation, a block of motivation and technology of media education, and a block of perceptive analytical activity" in the target-content component.

N.Yu. Khlizova shows a special purpose block, i.e. project-content, pedagogical conditions block, procedural and monitoring blocks separately. N. Yu. Khlizova gives conclusions based on the methods recommended by A. V. Fedorov in her research.

Ye.A.Stolbnikova's author's work on the development of media competence based on advertising includes three components. Diagnostic, that is, it is related to the level of media culture and the tasks of mastering it. The content-targeted component combines theoretical and practical elements, includes practical elements, technologies, tasks and recommendations, and serves to develop practical experiences in critical thinking. Ye.A.Stolbnikova's model ends with a traditional result component. This model has proven its effectiveness in practice.

B.A. Iskakov describes the process of developing the media culture of teachers in three stages as an example of information and educational resource centers. At the preparatory stage, it is aimed to approach media culture, media technologies and other types of situations as a special value of future English language teachers.

N.V. Chicherina offers the most complete picture. His work is based on the system of principles of development of communicative competence and media literacy integrated in a foreign language. This system envisages the integrated principles of media education and foreign language teaching. The researcher uses the principle of collective development of communicative competence and media literacy in this language when working with media culture texts in a foreign language; the principle of dialogue; the principle of interdisciplinary integration; the principle of intertextuality;

the principle of multiliteracy development; the principle of developing critical thinking; the principle of development of creative potential; highlights the principle of developing students' critical autonomy, which has an individual impact on the future English teacher. According to the author, the principle of collective development of communicative competence and media literacy in a foreign language, the principle of intertextuality, and the principle of multiliteracy development are highlighted for the first time in working with media culture texts in a foreign language, which are of particular importance in the context of language teaching and media education integration.

According to H. Kadirov, "Media stereotypes are often found in mass culture works of various genres. In the process of analyzing advertising media, it is important to study the situations, conditions of media text actions (subjects, place of action, place, historical period, etc.), characters, their values, ideas, language, facial expressions, gestures, costumes, will be focused on image methods" expresses the importance and necessity of the opinion. In the analysis of media stereotypes, pedagogues get an opportunity to deepen their knowledge about the features of the audiovisual works of the genre, its means of expression, the features and conditions of the media language, which are characteristic of the comedy genre of media culture. Media culture works will be directed towards a full understanding of media with the help of analytical and comparative interpretive skills as a result of performing creative tasks. The knowledge acquired by pedagogues based on the analysis of media culture works can be used in their practical activities.

So, in order to effectively organize work with the materials of media culture works, a modern teacher must have a good command of the main methods, tools and methods of various genres, forms and analysis. Therefore, many things in the educational process are determined by the existing personal attitude of the teacher towards media culture, the methods he uses in the educational process. Creating a strong creative, dialogic environment based on the free expression of one's opinions - all these factors promote their positive and effective impact on media education. This approach promotes the individuality of future English language teachers, their independent thinking allows us to come to the conclusion that it is appropriate to use active forms and methods that develop and stimulate by directly forming his abilities.

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